

Clews-Based Comparative Analysis for Power Sector and Land Use Change Scenarios in Ghana

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Energy Modelling Platform Global (EMP-G)

Context, Challenges, and Main Findings

Main challenges investigated

1. To investigate the impact of renewable energy on CO2 emissions and other nexus sectors.
2. The impact of increasing land for built-up areas on other components of the nexus

Research questions

1. What impact will the increase in RE have on emissions and other nexus components?
2. What impact would an increase in Built-up areas have on other land covers?

Main findings

1. RE and Nuclear are not cost-competitive (Base Case)
2. Increasing renewable energy share, reduced CO2 emission, and water demand for power generation.
3. Increasing land for built-up areas reduced agricultural land and a slight increase in the demand for public water supply

GHANA

Ghana Reference CLEWs Diagram

Scenarios

Applying the CLEWs framework, using the OSeMOSYS tool, the following scenarios were investigated.

Base Case

- Renewable Energy
Target: None

Renewable Energy

- Renewable Energy
Target: 10% by 2030 and
20% by 2070.

Land Cover Change

- Built-up area increases by
7% per annum.

Results

Power generation capacity for the base case and renewable energy target.

Base Case Power Generation Capacity

RE Scenario Power Generation Capacity

Results

Comparative analysis between the Base case and Renewable energy target.

ANNUAL EMISSION

WATER DEMAND

Results

Land use comparison between the Base case and the built-up land scenario

Base case Land Cover Types

Land Cover Change Scenario

Conclusion and Policy Insights

To achieve the set targets for Ghana, the country needs to follow the policies set out.

Recommended Steps

- Renewable energies and nuclear are not cost-competitive and should need a policy to ensure their integration into the energy mix
- Incentivize the adoption and integration of renewable energy by providing subsidies and tax incentives.
- Land for built-up areas should be halted by 2050 to conserve the land for forests

Future work

- Green hydrogen
- Modelling the decline of natural gas in the mid-2050s and the introduction of nuclear power in the energy mix.

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